

Gaddi, a Hindu community of the Western Himalayas

By Stephen Christopher, Tokyo Metropolitan University

Entry tags: Indic Religious Traditions, Christians in India, Radhasoami, Arya Samaj, Tribal Himalayan traditions, Śaiva traditions, Religious Group, Modern Hinduism, Hinduism, Sikh traditions

The Gaddis of Himachal Pradesh are a community of tribal Rajputs and Bhatt Brahmins, and five partially-assimilated Dalit castes. They straddle both sides of the Dhauladhar Mountains and share a matrix of commonalities often described as tribal -- distinct dialect, ritual practice, clan-based social organization, transhumant pastoralism, place-making ties to the mountains, and Shavite spiritual beliefs that are distinctly Gaddi. Gaddis are commonly called a tribe, although they have a complex history in being awarded Scheduled Tribe status in Kangra and ethnopolitical mobilizations are underway to include Dalits within the Gaddi tribal fold. The community is heterogeneous, spread across a large swath of the Western Himalayas extending into Kashmir. Primarily Shaivite, some low-status Gaddis have converted into a range of new spiritual beliefs. These include Protestantism, Sikhism, Devi worship, Radhasoami and Arya Samaj, among other Nirankar traditions.

Date Range: 1845 CE - 2018 CE

Region: Gaddis of the Western Himalayas -- Modern Period

Region tags: Asia, South Asia, India, Western India, Dhauladhar Mountains, North India, Western Himalayas

Gaddi geography, including transhumant routes and settled population centers, at its greatest extent to the present.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Wagner, Anya. 2013. *The Gaddi Beyond Pastoralism: Making Place in the Indian Himalayas*. New York: Berghahn Books.
- Source 2: Phillimore, Peter. 1982. "Marriage and Social Organisation among Pastoralists of the Dhauladhar (Western Himalaya)." PhD diss., University of Durham.
- Source 3: Christopher, Stephen. 2018. "Dalit Margins: Tribal Belonging and State Recognition in the Western Himalayas." PhD diss., Syracuse University.

Notes: Other important sources include: Singh, Chetan. 1997. "A strategy of interdependence: Gaddi, peasant and state in Himachal." In *From tribe to caste*, 374-386. Shima: Indian Institute of Advanced Study. Singh, Chetan. 2012. "Pastoral People and Shepherding Practices in the Western Himalaya (Himachal Pradesh): A Historical Perspective." In *Pastoral practices in High Asia: Agency of 'development' effected by modernisation, resettlement and transformation*, edited by Hermann Kreutzmann, 161-74.

Berlin: Springer. Sharma, Mahesh. 2015. "Ritual, Performance, and Transmission: The Gaddi Shepherds of Himachal Himalayas." *Oral Tradition* 29(2):271-90. Axelby, Richard. 2007. "It takes two hands to clap': How Gaddi shepherds in the Indian Himalayas negotiate access to grazing. *Journal of Agrarian Change* 7(1):35-75.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 2 URL: www.gabdika.com
- Source 2 Description: Community website including various Gaddi photos, songs and legends
- Source 3 URL: www.facebook.com/groups/gaddiecommunity
- Source 3 Description: Largest Gaddi networking Facebook page

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: gaddi.in
- Source 1 Description: Protestant website of Gaddi biblical materials in Hindi/Gaddi

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: Gaddi religious practices and beliefs often intersect with Mother Goddess (Devi) worship in Kangra (see Erndl, RDB) and with a range of Hindu beliefs mapped onto the landscape during the yearly Manimahesh pilgrimage. While it may be too strong to call these intersections "competitive", they do provide important arenas of communal affirmation and ethnic distancing between Gaddis and non-Gaddi mountain (Pahadi) groups.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: The paramount Gaddi ritual, a sheep sacrifice called nuala, is sometimes adopted by proximate Hindu communities. The yearly Manimahesh pilgrimage is inclusive and expresses pluralistic conceptions of Hinduism, as one might expect.

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

Notes: Gaddi expressions of Hinduism suffer from some of the same caste-based discriminations and forms of structural violence seen throughout India -- caste-based hierarchy, forms of symbolically polluting labor (exorcists, removers of animal carcasses,

ploughers and so on), exclusion of low-status groups from the inner sanctum of temples and from sacred highland pastureland, and strict caste endogamy.

Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: Gaddis are born into respective castes and clans which traditionally structured their vocations (Bhatt Brahmans as pujaris, Rajputs as shepherds and Dalit groups as menials, and so on). Gaddis have a limited set of ancestral deities, some of whom are generically Hindu and some of whom draw from a specifically Gaddi cosmology. These ancestral deities, along with family priests (kul purohit) are markers of inclusion within the Gaddi religious milieu.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: Although contested, Gaddi identity is generally thought to be ascribed by birth.

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: Although not officially patronized, Gaddis maintained close ties to the historic Raja of Chamba. In the contemporary period, political parties vie for Gaddi support as a generic vote bank and certain Gaddi MLAs are disproportionately concerned with Gaddi welfare and interject politics into ongoing contestation about Gaddi belonging.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Notes: Affiliation is involuntary and ascribed by birth.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 120000

Notes: The number of Gaddi speakers according to SIL International (<http://www.ethnologue.com>). This is merely one contested rubric and does not consider the complex entanglement of definitions and enumerations of Gaddis going back to the colonial period. Most population estimates do not seriously engage with the problem of Dalit groups who self-identify as Gaddi and are partially assimilated.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 90

Notes: The remainder are migratory workers often living in Delhi or working with season tourists in Goa, Leh and other stops on the so-called Hummus Trail (a network of sites associated with Israeli backpackers and hippie tourists).

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (not related to larger religious group)

Notes: There is an ongoing debate about whether the Gaddi caste system is enmeshed in, or parallel to, wider Kangra caste configurations. In general, the religious underpinnings of Gaddi castes draw from the generic logic of status hierarchy articulated as far back as Manu -- the so-called "book-view" of caste. Gaddi Dalits also draw from a wide swath of religious traditions, Hindu or otherwise, to find spiritual critiques of their caste subordination within the Gaddi community. In the tribal margins, these Gaddi Dalits occupy overlapping concentric circles linking Gaddi cosmology and religious practices to outside Kangri religious forms. And mainstream Gaddi religious practice is fully enmeshed in Himalayan Shaivism. Having laid out these important qualifications, however, it is safe to say that Gaddis think of their own religious forms as distinct from other Pahadi groups.

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

Notes: Gaddi religious hierarchy could be said to radiate from the Chaurasi Temple in Bharmaur, the axis mundi of Gaddi spirituality. Certainly Bhatt Brahman Pandits in famous Gaddi temples -- Kugti and Chaurasi, for example -- have prestige that extends across the Gaddi world. However, it is also correct to say that Gaddi spiritual authority is decentralized. Within an individual village or network of villages there may be a single Bhatt Brahman Gaddi Pandit who carries local prestige and is the primary ritual expert. This holds true for Gaddi Dalits as well. Since they are often barred a family priest due to casteism, they elect local figures within their caste who officiate over rituals (often called "joganu" or "jogi"). They carry local prestige.

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– No

Notes: Primarily they are orally recounted in various mediums from song -- bhajans and folk music by Hali-caste mistrals (ghudai) -- to stories told by Pandits and lay people.

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

Notes: Gaddis have a range of authoritative oral scriptures that speak to their cosmological relationship to Shiva, their communal creation and their ties to pastoralism. During the nuala ritual, Gaddi singers recount community-specific bhajans that affirm the tie between Shiva and Gaddis. Among Gaddi Dalits, there is a range of legends, oral accounts and contested "scriptures" that locate their castes as Gaddi or Gaddi aspiring. Sippis, in particular, recount oral scriptures linking their caste to Trilochan Mahadev, a deified Sippi who ties the caste community to the Gaddi tribe through being the tailor of Shiva. I argue that these Gaddi Dalit scriptures are often sites of identity contestation and are authoritative only within among specific Gaddi castes.

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– No

Notes: Although Shiva-ji gave various customs and habits to the Sippi Trilochan Mahadev, for example, there is no belief per se that Gaddi theology was imparted to any specific Gaddi or written down/formalized at any specific moment of time.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: Possible exception: Chaurasi Temple in Bharmaur.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– On persons

– At home

– Some public spaces

Notes: Visual imagery of Gaddiness extends across certain kinds of customary dress, symbolic markings along local pilgrimage routes, traditional facial tattooing (decorative), style of cap,

and iron whips used for flagellation usually sanctified in Bharmaur and installed in family temples and installed wherever Gaddis live in the Western Himalayas.

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Yes

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– No

Notes: Not doctrinal, but emphases are different among Gaddis -- i.e. the valuation of nomadic lifestyle (ghmantu) based on conceptions of Shiva-ji and place-making practices that localize deities in the mountains.

↳ Humans:

– No

↳ Other features of iconography:

– No

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: Sacred sites can be geomorphic Shivalings, highland pastures, the apex of Manimahesh Mountain, the seat of Shiva, and so on.

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

How strict is pilgrimage:

– Optional (common)

Notes: Pilgrimage is an important part of Gaddi life. It includes localized pilgrimage, usually day trips for livestock sacrifices to family deities (jatar and jagra). These are usually kin-organized pilgrimages important to place-making strategies in the Himalayas (see Anja Wagner). At a broader level, the Manimahesh Yatra is an important pilgrimage undertaken by many Gaddis. The journey from Hardsar to Kugti and Dal Lake is an important circuit for Gaddi religious life in Bharmaur and is differently experienced by the Sippi caste as evidence of their priestly shamanic functions as Balode (evidence for their formal inclusion as ST Gaddis). Overall, pilgrimage is both a space of communal celebration and a practice of status negotiation and identity formation/exclusion.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Field doesn't know

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: Reincarnation

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

↳ In a human form:

– Yes

Notes: Typically human, although reincarnation could entail other non-human species or plant forms based on karmic deeds.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

↳ Cremation:

– Yes

Notes: Traditionally a Brahman caste of comparatively lower social status named Chhatri would officiate over Gaddi death rituals. Gaddis nearly always cremate bodies in local cremation grounds (shamsham ghat). When feasible, ashes are poured into the Ganga River in Haridwar and a local Pandit keeps the Gaddi family lineage records.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: Many stories are recounted of Shiva-ji taking human form.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: This is contested, although most Gaddis believe that Shiva-ji is the ultimate Godhead from which everything emanates.

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

Notes: Not exactly chthonic, although Gaddis conventionally believe that for six months Shiva-ji lives inside Manimahesh Mountain through the access point of Dal Lake. Gaddi transhumance is tied to this cycle of Shiva-ji being underground/overground.

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

Notes: Not a blood kin, but the creator of Gaddis as proto humans.

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– Yes [specify]: Creator god of Gaddis. Giver of Gaddi lifestyle, habits and dress to Gaddis via Trilochan Mahadev.

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: Unquestionably good, although Shiva-ji is an erotic-ascetic (Doniger) and as such prone to ethical reversals.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Shiva-ji is worshiped throughout South Asia.

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– No

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– No

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: Future knowledge depends on the belief of the individual, although Gaddis generally have faith that Shiva-ji is just and all-knowing.

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– Yes

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– Yes

Notes: not only does Shiva-ji take many forms, but Gaddis worship cognate ancestral deities and nature spirits. Gaddi religious practices are part of the expected syncretism of Hinduism.

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– No

Notes: Very rarely. Oftentimes Shiva-ji communicates with Gaddis through an oracle.

↳ In dreams:

– No

Notes: Not unheard of, however.

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

Notes: Both celas (oracles) and everyday people possessed during ritual.

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

Notes: This is the domain of so-called witch doctors (tantra-mantra) -- normally Hali in Kangra.

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: Bhatt Brahmins for life cycle rituals and during high rituals (nuala, for example) and Halis for spirit exorcism (connected to both Shiva-ji and local Devi Mother Goddess).

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: Through sighting (darsan) in geomorphic and personal form.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: Seen, sensed, embodied.

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: Gaddis believe in a range of natural spirits named pahariya who can be afflictive.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: Many oral narrative recount how Shiva-ji understands the hidden motivations of actors. Sippis recount how Shiva-ji punished a Gaddi for his arrogant motives in trying to summit Mahimahesh to take darshan, for example.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: The pantheon of Gaddi cosmology, from Shiva-ji downwards, has knowledge of hidden motives, can observe human action and intention in every domain (although some spirits are localized to specific natural formations -- trees and highland pastures, for example), and in general can be both afflictive and benevolent.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

Notes: Gaddis often perform celebratory rituals for Shiva-ji when they receive a promised boon based on reciprocal prayers (len-den in Hindi; sukhan in Gaddi dialect).

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

Notes: If a reciprocal prayer is broken -- meaning the divine reward is given but the Gaddi actor does not respond with a ritual celebration -- Shiva-ji and a range of Gaddi-related deities can become afflictive. Moreover, some Halis (the lowest status group of the Gaddi community) are tormented by Gaddi deities and, as a response, have converted to Protestantism.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: Certainly with respect to the quality of harvest and to meteorological phenomenon such as rainfall.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: For many Gaddis, their family deities and Shiva-ji himself are major sources of well-being and foundational to identity.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: When slighted or abused by reneging on a sukhan (prayer for some boon with accompanying ritual celebration).

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

Notes: Gaddi nature spirits can be rapacious and are known to steal the milk from livestock, among other forms of hunger.

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: Gaddi nature spirits and Gaddi-related monsters (rakshas) can exhibit a range of emotions -- hunger, anger, jealousy, fear. These emotions are recounted by Gaddis sometimes in connection with the ancestral deities (kul devi-devta) and sometimes in relationship to place-based spirits who are tamed/propitiated.

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– Yes

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

Notes: With Shiva-ji at the apex, ancestral deities as a localized mode of intercession, and a range of nature spirits and forms of witchcraft (jadu-tona in Hindi; opra-sopra in Gaddi) drawing from malign spirits.

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

Notes: Shiva-ji in his erotic-ascetic emanation is localized to the Himalayas, as are a range of Gaddi nature spirits and naga deities.

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Gaddi spirits require forms of etiquette when in sacred high-altitude spaces. Other social breaches can be punished by Gaddi deities.

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

↳ Food:

– Yes

Notes: Sheep and/or goat sacrifices are mandated at prescribed times.

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

Notes: Especially highland pastures and mountain crossings -- dangerous and rarefied places where we would expect heightened norms surrounding screaming, cursing, joking, defecating, cooking and so on.

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

Notes: The maintenance of installed deities (murti) and associated symbols (shivling, trishul, sangal).

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

Notes: Gaddis are not particularly sex-prohibitive compared to other Hindu groups in North India. Gaddis often relate tales of the lax sexual practices of polygamy and sister exchange (batta satta) between families. Social norms involving sexuality have been tightening due to

increased Hinduization and mixing with Punjabi forms.

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

↳ Incest:

– Yes

Notes: As is normal across many lay practitioners of Shaivism.

↳ Other sexual practices:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Notes: Especially oaths between Gaddi actors and supernatural hosts.

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

Notes: Not only care about, often authorize.

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– No

Notes: However, Gaddi shepherds often describe their transhumance as physically dangerous and courting forms of risk. Since such work is inseparable from Shiva-ji, it is plausible to describe risk taking as a form of spiritually-authorized behavior.

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– No

Notes: Not very much. Gossip is an essential part of Gaddi village life.

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

Notes: Such rituals are inextricably bound up with the supernatural deities themselves.

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– No

Notes: Gaddi Shaivism is not proselytizing.

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– No

Notes: Gaddi Shaivism and popular forms of everyday Hinduism is often a justification for casteism and social hierarchy. Goddess (Devi) worship among Gaddi Dalits, along with Christian, Sikh, Radhasoami and Arya Samaj conversion among Gaddi Dalits pushes adherents into religious traditions that care more about economic and social fairness.

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

Notes: In highland pastures and mountain crossings.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: Gaddi family deities care about the overall wellbeing of the clan segmentation.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

|

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

Notes: Karma can be seen as impersonal causal effect, but also supernatural punishment is often seen as specifically directed by shortcomings of actors (failure to reciprocate, for example).

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– Yes

Notes: All means of misfortune can be attributed to supernatural punishment.

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

Notes: Many Gaddi stories exist of supernatural deities (especially nag deities) punishing Gaddis for selfishly pursuing their own projects and enrichment without asking permission. This takes many forms -- building mountain footbridges without consulting the local nag deities, for example.

↳ Done randomly:

– I don't know

Notes: Spiritual motivations are often given by Gaddis for egregious disasters and misfortunes.

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

Notes: Perhaps not as much as other traditions, although boons and misfortunes are often located within a supernatural arena depending on the religious temperament of the individual and local norms.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural punishments can be seen by Gaddis (depending on the individual) as causing financial ruin, disease, misfortunes of all kinds, sterility, loss of prestige, failure and so on.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

Notes: This depends on individual belief. Some Gaddis maintain that Shiva-ji is the high god and ultimate arbiter. Others maintain conceptual distinction between Shiva-ji and nature spirits, family deities, naga spirits and so on.

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– No

- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Depending on the individual, karma is an explanatory model for everyday occurrences.
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:
 - No
 - Notes: Luck is less explanatory than karma, but depends on individual.
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
 - No
 - Notes: Battle is not a commonplace thing.
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
 - Yes

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - Yes

Notes: Similar to punishment, reward is a diffuse concept connected to karmic deeds and impacting all areas of life, depending on the beliefs on the individual. This model holds true for most Gaddis, although its intensity depends on the person.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Weakly present

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– No

Notes: Gaddi religion does not strongly regulate moral behavior or move into moral normative explanations -- other than the causal relationship between action and karmic outcomes.

↳ Moral norms apply to:

– All individuals within society

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: Not any more than generic Hindu beliefs entail.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Notes: Just generic Hindu fasting like during Karva Chauth.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Ritual obligations can be taxing on time and finances.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– No

Notes: Gaddis are not marked by distinct ethical precepts outside of expected Hindu beliefs (with some notable exceptions such as allowed intoxicants as per some Shavite traditions).

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Notes: There is the conventional expectation for executing life cycle rituals.

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– I don't know

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– I don't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Bhatt Brahmins are the ritual experts, although there is a lot of leeway for Gaddi Rajputs in the execution of festivals. Spiritual interpretation is concentrated among Brahmins but can be diffuse because lay people can become possessed and act as spiritual intermediaries and oracles.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– Yes

Notes: Sur is the traditional Gaddi intoxicant, but can also include hash (charas).

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– No

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Gaddis are commonly called a "tribe" in scholarly literature. This name reflects the tribal scheduling of Gaddi Rajputs and Brahmans in Kangra and those Gaddi-aligned castes living within the tribal-reserved areas in Bharmaur. It is more exact, however, to describe Gaddis as a generic community title encompassing high- and low-status groups who speak Gaddi dialect and share Herderian commonalities. The Gaddi community is further complexified by the division between Scheduled Tribe (ST) Brahmans and Rajputs and Scheduled Caste (SC) Halis, Dhogris, Badis, Sippis and Rihare. These low-caste groups are variously aligned in ethnopolitical mobilizations for ST status as Gaddis in Kangra. As such, the Gaddis can best be thought of as a community of tribal and Dalit castes and a contested identity grounded in state recognition and forms of emic exclusion.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Some Gaddis receive IRDB welfare assistance based on poverty level and remoteness. This includes subsidized staple foods like rice and pulses in remote depots.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Notes: Not formally institutionalized, although village-level temples often provide free meals and sometimes shelter indigent Gaddis.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Federal relief under the SC/ST reservation.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Notes: Although not institutionalized care, elderly are typically cared for by children and grandchildren. It is rare for Gaddi elders to age independent of their blood relations, communal affines and caste community (sarik, biradari).

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Notes: Gaddi children mostly attend Hindi-medium government schools and do not have formal institutions to preserve Gaddi culture and language.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: Gaddis are either Scheduled Caste or Scheduled Tribe depending on caste and locality. The struggle for ST benefits among Kangra Gaddi Rajputs and Bhatt Brahmans, which came to a successful end in 2002, entailed auto-ethnographies, government anthropologists conducting regional surveys, and ethnopolitical efforts to construct tribal purity. Such efforts put Gaddis in close contact with government bureaucracy and placed them in the paradoxical situation of needing to demonstrate their tribality in order to be have "modern" social citizenship and receive positive discrimination. The Gaddi campaign ended in 2002, although Gaddi Dalits continue to stage events and put pressure on the government and various institutional bureaucracies to enter the ST quota.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: However, there is Gaddi village-wide assistance offered during the cultivation of individual rice fields (juar). Such rituals are important forms of sociality aimed at guaranteeing food availability for individual Gaddi families.

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: However, foodstuff was traditionally exchanged between Gaddis and other Kangra castes (such as exchange of walnuts for staple foods between Gaddis and Dumne).

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Yes

Notes: Gaddi villages are equally invested in the maintenance of gravity-flow irrigation systems (kulh) to crops and potable water (see J. Mark Baker).

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: However, MNREGA funds are often spent on village water management systems.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Notes: However, Gaddi shepherds traditionally laid down the footpaths and mountain passes that linked pastureland and villages.

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Notes: Not exactly taxes, but at the village level Gaddis are oftentimes conventionally required to donate money, crop share and/or a livestock for communal feasts.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: The British peasantized and settled migratory Gaddis for taxation purposes, although they were never classified as a so-called Criminal Tribe.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Notes: Not institutionalized in a formal sense, but Gaddi civic disputes are often adjudicated by local political systems (panchayat). Moreover, there are democratically-elected village officials (often reserved as SC/ST based on demographics) such as pradhan, uppradhan, patwari and so on.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The formal Indian legal system and the everyday state.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Notes: Gaddis rarely outcaste members. Such cases are few and usually based on prohibited intercaste

eloping.

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The federal Indian legal code.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Notes: Although traditionally Gaddis may have been a standing army force for the petty kingdoms in Chamba. The ethnonym "Gaddi" may refer to the military banner under which Gaddi stood (based on O.C. Handa's historiography).

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Kangra Gaddi men are frequently recruited into the military as many local bases exist. This is a viable lifeway for many Gaddi men, tying their martial past to the present. Many Gaddis join the Dogra Regiment and receive various physical exceptions (height and weight) based on being recruited from a "border area".

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Indian army, police and Border Security Forces.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: Occasionally Gaddi dialect is written using Devanagari.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: Gaddis have a ritual calendar and community-specific designations for time cycles (Bhadron and Asoj, for example, between mid-August and late-September -- connected to the pastoral cycle and rituals at Chaurasi Temple in Bharmaur).

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

Notes: Depending on remoteness and locality, Gaddis forage herbs and mountain vegetables, practice transhumant pastoralism or localized forms of so-called "flock duty", fish in rivers and hunt in mountains, and, perhaps most centrally, practice scratch- and terraced-farming.

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

–Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Based on poverty and quota, Gaddis receive subsidized core foods from the Indian government.